

TASK 1.5 ENGAGING YOUNG PEOPLE IN MOVING ACTIVITIES: Engaging young people in mountain areas in the Long Term Vision for Rural Areas

1. Why?

2022 is the European Year of Youth, and as such our focus in T1.5 is of utmost importance. According to the recent [Euromontana](#) report, 'Europe's mountain areas are facing a constant threat to their attractiveness, especially among younger generations. In some regions, the rural exodus of young mountain people and the ageing of the population endanger the demographic balance, social cohesion, and economic appeal of our mountains. Yet, the new generations are the future of our territories'. As such, it is vital to include the viewpoints and engagement on young people into the MOVING project research activities, so they can both shape and participate in the sustainable development of Europe's Mountain areas and industries. In 2021, Euromontana gathered the views of 1134 young people living in mountain areas across 20 European countries. The results identified that these young people want to remain living (and potentially) working in Europe's Mountain areas. Such motivation to live in these mountain areas can only continue if development in these mountain areas continues to be sustainable and attractive to young people in terms of being able to appreciate the surrounding natural environment and have the potential to work and live in the area (either through commuting or working in the mountainous area). Furthermore, given the [Europarc Youth Manifesto](#) calls for the engagement of young people in connecting to their communities and developing sustainable futures, and the widely signed [UNIMONT manifesto](#) which highlights drawing attention to the specificities of mountain areas, MOVING is well placed to add to and further such engagement and discussions. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, is the current Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas which identifies areas of action towards stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas and communities.

As such, the work of Task 1.5 (engaging young people living in mountain regions) is of huge current importance. We propose to engage young people through a flexible participatory workshop (1 per region), through which we will seek to target young people in particular. For the purposes of this work, we will follow the United Nations definition for young people: "the United Nations, for statistical purposes, defines those persons between the ages of 15 and 24 as youth without prejudice to other definitions by Member States". However, we also realise that the young farmer definition (those aged 40 and under) may be a better fit for some partners and we accommodate this adaptation if useful to your case study. The voices of young people in mountain rural development are important because ensuring the sustainability of mountain areas will require positive engagement of young people who either are already, or may desire in the future, to base themselves in (or return to) these mountain areas (i.e., those who identify as belonging to the MRL). We encourage you to draw on the materials for the [current Long Term Vision for Rural Areas](#) and the [Inventory of Future Dreams](#) by the young from the H2020 [Ruralization](#) project

This participatory workshop can be somewhat flexible to address the issues of most relevance to your region/ value chain. The workshop will take place between June 2022 and mid October 2022, allowing some flexibility to meet your specific regional calendars. The results from the workshop can feed into the participatory aspects of WP4 (e.g., participatory workshop within T4.5 to be held in late 2022 which has a focus on sustainability, resilience and vulnerability), the thematic clusters in WP5 (i.e., what issues are of most importance to young people? Or youth engagement as a specific cluster). Finally, the results will feed into the foresight exercises in WP6. Reporting of this workshop will be completed by October 28th 2022.

Finally, before Month 40, each region will promote the latest and ongoing MOVING results to children at school age, with a focus on local schools in the MRL or nearby urban areas. The aim of this additional activity will be to raise the awareness of children about the potential of mountain areas in the provision of public and private goods and the vulnerabilities they face. More guidance on this additional activity will follow in 2023.

2. What?

The aim of the participatory workshop is to gather and explore the views of local young people (i.e., in the MRL) on sustainable mountain development of their region and how the VC assemblage can support their vision of SMD. In other words, this workshop will go beyond simply exploring and analysing the value chain, instead looking at how the value chain can help to further their vision of sustainable mountain development. In terms of the benefits that the young people may obtain from participation, these include: an additional opportunity to feed into policy recommendations on sustainable development (and climate change and the VC) in their area, increase their professional and personal networks. There will also be opportunities for the young people to participate in other MOVING activities and co-author a report based on this workshop.

3. Who?

Within this task you may engage with any young people between 15 and 24 (adhering to the UN definition), who live (or wish to return to live) within the MRL. However, if 40 and under (to fit with the young farmer definition) fits in your MRL then please utilise this definition. You should/ can draw on existing youth groups in the area (e.g., young farmers groups, conservation groups, school groups, summer school groups, rural youth parliaments), who will a) have an interest/connection to the MRL/ VC, b) have an interest in local Sustainable Mountain Development.

Please try to draw on existing groups, and link onto existing meetings to ensure efficiency and strong participation through existing groups.

4. When?

We propose that you aim to hold your event between June and September 2022. Adhering to this timescale means that outputs and findings from D4.3 and the workshops from D4.4 can feed into this youth engagement work, as well as allowing enough flexibility to fit around the specific calendars in your regions. Short reports on the workshops will be due by Friday 28th October. Please also be aware that the T4.5 participatory workshop is due to be held between September and December 2022, although the audience for this may differ and hence be a separate activity to T1.5.

To be prepared to run your W1.5 events between June (or earlier) and mid October 2022, we suggest you begin to contact existing youth groups (and then MAP members) as early as March 2022 to gauge their interest and availability. You may also be able to mention this T1.5 work whilst you are carrying out the interviews for the Value Chain Analysis work in WP4.

We envisage the participatory event for T1.5 can be held either in-person or virtually, depending on a) the covid situation in your MRL at the time of the event, and b) the preference of your MAP members and young people. As such, we have devised an event that can work in either in-person or virtual situations.

5. How?

The table below highlights the steps you may want to take to organise the participatory workshop/ event, along with some additional things to potentially consider at each step.

Steps	Details	Example	Things to remember
1	Identify (existing if possible) group of young people to engage with for the workshop: e.g., rural youth parliament, summer school, scout group, youth action group, school class, young farmers group, college students. Please also check your budgets for WP1 travel and subsistence to see if an online or in-person workshop would be more appropriate in terms of resource use. Please also keep in mind to keep a small budget for the additional youth engagement activities in 2023.	e.g., for use in Scotland, this might be the Cairngorms Youth Action Project (CYAP)	Do you need to submit a specific ethics application to conduct this participatory event? Do you need to obtain any additional clearance/ permission to work with young people? e.g. in Scotland this is a PVG (Prevention of Vulnerable Groups) and/or clearance from Disclosure Scotland. Do you have any existing links to youth

			organisations through your MAP?
2	Identify the existing vision of Sustainable Mountain Development from young people in the area (if it exists) and base your event on this. Explore how the Long Term Vision for Rural areas may fit in your area.	e.g., in Scotland, we might look at the mission/ vision statement of CYAP and/or Cairngorms National Park Authority draft partnership plan	Draw on your MAP members to help with this and/or the information you found from completing D4.3.
3	Identify the 3 MAP members best placed to present at the event regarding sustainable mountain development in the MRL.	e.g. for us, perhaps someone representing the whisky industry, water industry and tourism/ national park	Contact potentially interested MAP members and offer some tentative times to hold the event? These MAP members can be young people too if you wish, but there is no expectation or requirement for this.
4	Organise an appropriate date for the meeting. If possible, you can link into one of the youth group's existing meetings.	e.g., run the event after a CYAP meeting or CNPA meeting.	Try to avoid times of year/week/day that would be difficult for your young people. Perhaps try to link onto an existing youth event.
5	If in person organise room and catering. If online, organise meeting software.		Draw on your MAP members to publicise the event.
6	Hold event		Remember to organise workshop materials, consent forms

Objectives of the 2-hour online/in-person meeting:

Workshop activity	Time	Tasks
Introductions	15 minutes	Check happy to record if appropriate and take photographs

<p>Highlight work of MOVING to date to group of young people i.e., results from WP3, WP4 and the potential connections to youth aspects</p>	<p>15 minutes</p>	<p>Prepare short presentation on the findings of MOVING to date that might be of interest to this youth group</p>
<p>3 MAP member presentations pitch their visions for mountain areas: to highlight how their work informs/connects (or attempts to inform) to the MRL's Sustainable Mountain Development</p>	<p>30 minutes (3 x 5-minute presentations + 15-minute Q&A)</p>	<p>Work with the MAP members to guide them through the presentation preparation i.e., potentially through a preparation call/meeting. Try to pick MAP members that will be engaging and informative</p>
<p>Small group discussions with project team, MAP presenters and young people to gather:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Their views of the findings How do you see the future of the region in 2040? How they would improve the sustainability and resilience of the VC What can be done to strengthen the role of young people in building the present and future of the mountain region? 	<p>30 minutes</p>	<p>Organise break out groups/ small tables of roughly 4-5 participants to gather their views of the MOVING findings and the MAP presentations; Explore how they would improve the sustainability and resilience of the VC; and the role/opportunities for young people in VC/MRL. Record responses either verbally or written down (per group).</p> <p>MOVING partners to facilitate discussions and MAP members to rotate between the groups to answer any questions and help with producing findings.</p>
<p>End session –</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Closing discussion Highlight that short report will be issued detailing the presentations and discussions and that the proposed visions will feed into T4.5 workshops Present opportunities for further engagement in MOVING activities 	<p>15 minutes</p>	<p>MOVING partners to facilitate closing discussion and highlight next steps.</p>

6. Reporting

Please upload your report (template in Annex 1) to the VRE by Friday 28th October 2022, as well as recording your findings in a new tab in the M&E reporting template (please also upload this to the VRE).

In month 40 (Jan 2024) Hutton will finalise the full report for D1.5 which will include not only a summary of the partner reports from these participatory workshops, but also how we have used existing materials from WP3 and WP4 in 2023 (see point 7), as well as reporting on the young M&E metrics.

7. Other youth requirements to address

As well as the participatory workshop held in 2022, we will also engage with young people through:

field visits and activities will be promoted with children at school age. Special agreements are negotiated with local schools in mountain and nearby urban areas to raise the awareness of children about the potential of mountain areas in the provision of public and private goods and the vulnerabilities they face.

In these activities we will highlight the findings of MOVING to date (i.e., WP3 and WP4). We (Hutton) will issue more guidance in this in late 2022/ early 2023, but please keep this in mind that this additional activity will take place in 2023.

8. Annex 1: Reporting Template

Please complete the following template by Friday 14th October and upload to the VRE (specific folder to be given nearer the time).

Section	Detail
Date and time of event:	
Was the event online/ in-person/ hybrid?	
Number of participants:	
Main activities of event	<i>Roughly 1 paragraph</i>
Main recommendations for sustainable mountain development i.e. the proposed visions connecting to the LTVRA i.e. summary answers to these questions: a. How do you see this	<i>Roughly 1 paragraph per vision</i>

<p>future of the region in 2040?</p> <p>b. How they would improve the sustainability and resilience of the VC</p> <p>c. What can be done to strengthen the role of young people in building the present and future of the mountain region?</p>	
<p>Role of VC in local Sustainable Mountain Development (if any)</p>	<p><i>Roughly 1 paragraph</i></p>
<p>Any other information of interest/ use to WP4.5</p>	<p><i>Roughly 1 paragraph</i></p>
<p>Any information of interest/ use to WP5</p>	<p><i>Roughly 1 paragraph</i></p>
<p>Any information of interest/ use to WP6</p>	<p><i>Roughly 1 paragraph</i></p>
<p>Do you think there would be interested in a youth focussed EU MAP event?</p>	<p>Yes / No</p>
<p>If yes, do you have any suggestions for the topic?</p>	<p><i>Roughly 1 paragraph</i></p>
<p>Anything else you would like to add</p>	

If you have any questions or would like any support throughout this process, please contact Rachel (Rachel.creaney@hutton.ac.uk) from the Scottish/ UK team.

9. References

EUROMONTANA, 2022. Being young in a mountain area. Mountain youth's needs in 2022 and aspirations for the future: [2022-01-24-Being-young-in-a-mountain-area_FinalReport_EN.pdf \(euromontana.org\)](#)

EUROPARC: [EUROPARC Youth Manifesto - EUROPARC Federation](#)

European Commission, 2021: [A long-term vision for the EU's rural areas](#)

Ruralization project: [Ruralization EU – Ruralization supports knowledge-based policies to make rural dreams of young Europeans true](#)

Ruralisation, 2021: [Inventory of futures dreams by the youth: technical report](#)

United Nations: [Youth | United Nations](#)

UNIMONT, 2021. [UNIMONT Manifesto](#)

Source: MOVING H2020

